

Task collection

This appendix contains the task collection* and mapping for levels of difficulty and errors for variables, loops and functions.

The task ID provides information about the level (or 'class') of difficulty: C1 stands for 'class 1', C2 for 'class 2' and C3 for 'class 3'. For example, task V1C1 is mapped to 'class 1', task L2C2 to 'class 2. etc.

* The tasks were collected from different online resources during the desk review.

1.1 Task collection variables

V1C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre>1 a = 200 2 a = 20 3 print(a)</pre>
Correct answer	20
Expected Error(s)	<p>1) output: 220 Values assigned to the variable will sum up instead of remembering only one, last assigned value.</p> <p>2) output: a Symbolic name of the variable will print out, instead of the value of the variable.</p> <p>3) output: 200 Variable remembers only the initial value.</p>

V2C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre>1 a = 100 2 a = 20 3 print('a')</pre>
Correct answer	a
Expected Error(s)	<p>1) output: 120 Values assigned to the variable will sum up instead of remembering only one, last assigned value.</p> <p>2) output: 20 Value of the variable will be printed, instead of the symbolic name.</p> <p>3) output: 100 Variable remembers only the initial value.</p>

V3C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 a = a+1 3 print(a) </pre>
Correct answer	101
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: a+1</p> <p>Variable value is a string rather than its previous incremented value/ variable holds an unevaluated expression instead of being incremented; known misconception about equal sign which students often replace with the math equation.</p>

V4C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 b = a 3 print (a,b) </pre>
Correct answer	100 100
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: a b</p> <p>Not assigning the variable value to another variable.</p>

V5C1

Task	<p>Given the following code, what is the output? Provide the answer in a free text field.</p> <pre> 1 a = 100 2 b = 20 3 a = 20 4 print (a,b) </pre>
Correct answer	20 20
Expected Error(s)	<p>output: 100 20</p> <p>Variable remembers the first value while ignoring the reassignment of the variable value.</p>

V6C1

Task	Is the following statement true or false? <i>"Variables always receive a particular default value upon creation."</i> <input type="checkbox"/> true <input type="checkbox"/> false
Correct answer	false
Expected Error(s)	true → Variables receive a particular default value upon creation.

V7C1

Task	Is the following statement true or false? <i>"The two segments $x = 1$; and $1 = x$; are equivalent."</i> <input type="checkbox"/> true <input type="checkbox"/> false
Correct answer	false
Expected Error(s)	true → Primitive assignment works in both directions.

V1C2

Task	Write a piece of python code to display the age of Mara who is seven years old and Max who is 11 years old. Calculate how old Mara and Max are together and print the result.
Correct answer	Different ways of implementation, e.g. <pre>age_mara = 7 age_max = 11 sum = age_mara + age_max print(sum)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No 'meaningful' naming of variables.

V2C2

Task	<p>Given the following code:</p> <pre>1 c = 1 2 3 def add(): 4 c = c+2 5 print(c) 6 7 add()</pre> <p>The program tries to print the variable called 'c' but it does not work and provides an error. Find the error(s) and correct the code. Don't change the first line of the given template! Write the corrected code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Use the global keyword to modify the variable from inside the function:</p> <pre>c = 1 def add(): global c c = c+2 print(c) add()</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Scope error - the program tries to modify the global variable c from inside the function.
Comment	This task refers not only to variables, but also to functions.

Task	<p>Given the following code:</p> <pre> 1 def find_max(n1, n2) 2 num1 = n1 3 num2 = n2 4 5 if num1 > num2: 6 result = num1 7 elif num2 > num1: 8 result = num2 9 else: 10 result = num1 11 return result 12 find_max(34,77) 13 print(result) </pre> <p>The program tries to print the variable called 'result' but it does not work and provides an error. Find the error(s) and correct the code. Write the corrected code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>The function itself needs to be assigned to a variable, then it can be printed:</p> <pre> def find_max(n1, n2) num1 = n1 num2 = n2 if num1 > num2: result = num1 elif num2 > num1: result = num2 else: result = num1 return result maxNum = find_max(34,77) print(maxNum) </pre>
Expected Error(s)	Scope error - the program tries to print the variable result created inside of the function.
Comment	This task refers not only to variables, but also to functions

VIC3

Task	Write a loop that sums the values 1 through "end", inclusive. "end" is a variable that we will define later. So For example, if we define "end" to be 6, your code should print out the result "21" (which is 1+2+3+4+5+6). Do not include input statements and do not define "end" to a specific value. We will do this later.
Correct answer	Multiple implementations, e.g.: <pre>sum = 0 i = 0 while i <= end: sum += 1 i +=1 print(sum)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple errors.

1.2 Task collection loops

L1C1

Task	Print I as long as I is less than 6: <pre>1 i = 1 2 <input type="text"/> i < 6 <input type="text"/> 3 print(i) 4 i +=1</pre> <p>Fill in the gaps</p>
Correct answer	while :
Expected Error(s)	Usage of if statement instead of a while loop, wrong syntax.

L2C1

Task	Loop through the items in the fruits list: <pre>1 fruits = ['apple', 'banana', 'cherry'] 2 <input type="text"/>x<input type="text"/>fruits<input type="text"/> 3 print(x)</pre> <p>Fill in the gaps</p>
Correct answer	for in :
Expected Error(s)	Usage of while instead of for, wrong syntax.

L3C1

Task	Stop the loop if i is 3: <pre>1 i = 1 2 while i < 6: 3 if i == 3: 4 <input type="text"/> 5 i += 1</pre> <p>Fill in the gap</p>
Correct answer	break
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the break statement.

L4C1

Task	<p>Print a message once the condition is false:</p> <pre> 1 i = 1 2 while i < 6: 3 print(i) 4 i += 1 5 <input type="text"/> 6 print('i is no longer less than 6.')</pre> <p>Fill in the gap</p>
Correct answer	else:
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the else statement, wrong syntax.

L5C1

Task	<pre> 1 num = 10 2 while num > 3: 3 num -= 1 4 print(num)</pre> <p>What does this loop print? Write the result in the free text field. Use a comma to separate a new line.</p>
Correct answer	9,8,7,6,5,4,3
Expected Error(s)	1) off-by-one error and 2) misconception that a loop halts as soon as the loop condition is false, rather than first finishing the loop's body.

L1C2

Task	<p>Convert the following into code that uses a while loop:</p> <pre> 2 4 6 8 10 Goodbye!</pre> <p>Write your code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	<p>For example:</p> <pre> i=2 while i<12: print(i) i+=2 print("Goodbye!")</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Off-by-one error, wrong syntax of a while loop.

L2C2

Task	<p>Convert the following into code that uses a for loop:</p> <pre> 2 4 6 8 10 Goodbye!</pre> <p>Write your code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	<p>For example:</p> <pre> for x in range (2,12,2): print(x) print ("Goodbye!")</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Off-by-one error, wrong syntax of a for loop.

L3C2

Task	<p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 def calculate_factorial(n): 2 result = 1 3 for i in range(1, n): 4 result = result * i 5 return result 6 7 print(calculate_factorial(5))</pre> <p>The function is designed to calculate the factorial of a given number n. If we run it for e.g. n=5, we would expect the output to be 120 (1*2*3*4*5 = 120). The code runs without any problem but gives an output of 24 instead of 120.</p> <p>Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	Change the range for the for loop to include the number n itself (in line 3) for I in range (1, n+1)
Expected Error(s)	Off-by-one error.

L4C2

Task	<p>We want to have the following output of a code snippet:</p> <pre>The count is: 1 The count is: 2 The count is: 3 The count is: 4 The count is: 5 That's it!</pre> <p>The given code snippet is:</p> <pre>1 count = 1 2 while (count < 5): 3 print('The count is:', count) 4 print("That's it!")</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>1) Adjust the condition for the while loop (in line 2), e.g.:</p> <pre>while (count <= 5)</pre> <p>2) Add a counter (in line 4)</p> <pre>count +=1</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Infinite loop, off-by-one error.

L5C2

Task	<p>We want to print a rectangle pattern with 8 rows and 4 columns of stars. It should look like this:</p> <pre>* *</pre> <p>The given code snippet is:</p> <pre>1 for name in range(8): 2 for j in range(4): 3 print('*', end = ' ') 4 print()</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Intend the nested loop:</p> <pre>for name in range(8): for j in range(4): print('*', end='') print()</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Nested loops.

L2C3

Task	Write a program to display all prime numbers within a range Note: A Prime Number is a whole number greater than 1 whose only factors are 1 and itself. For our example, don't define the range yet.
Correct answer	Multiple implementations, e.g.: <pre>print("Prime numbers between", start, "and", end, "are:") for num in range(start, end + 1): if num > 1: for i in range(2, num): if (num % i) == 0: break else: print(num)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple errors.

1.3 Task collection functions

F1C1

Task	Create a function named "my_function" and fill in the gap: <pre>1 <input type="text"/> 2 print("Hello from a function")</pre>
Correct answer	<pre>def my_function():</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of how to define a function, syntax errors.

F2C1

Task	Execute a function named "my_func" and fill in the gap: <pre>1 def my_func(): 2 print("Hello from a function") 3 4 <input type="text"/></pre>
Correct answer	<pre>my_func()</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of how to call a function, syntax errors.

F3C1

Task	Inside a function with two parameters, print the first parameter and fill in the gap: <pre>1 def my_func(firstname, lastname): 2 print(<input type="text"/>)</pre>
Correct answer	<pre>fname</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of how to pass arguments/ parameters.

F4C1

Task	<p>Let the function return the x parameter + 5 and fill in the gaps:</p> <pre> 1 def my_func(x): 2 <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> </pre>
Correct answer	return x + 5
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the return statement, syntax errors.

F1C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output: (7,8)</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def add(a,b): 2 a=a+5, b=b+5 3 4 result = add(3,2) 5 print(result) </pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	Change line 2 and add the return statement: return a+5, b+5
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the return statement.

F2C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output: Hi, Ada Lovelace!</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def greeting(firstname, lastname): 2 def getFullName(): 3 return firstname + " " + lastname 4 print("Hi, " + "!") 5 6 greeting('Ada', 'Lovelace')</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	Change line 4 to call the inner function: <code>print("Hi, " + getFullName() + "!")</code>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the nesting of functions.

F3C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output: Emma 25</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre> 1 def fun1(name, age=20): 2 print(name, age) 3 4 fun1('Emma')</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Rewrite the code in the free text field</p>
Correct answer	Add the second parameter in line 3: <code>fun1('Emma', 25)</code>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of the parameter passing/ default parameter.

F4C2

Task	<p>The following code should sum up two values by using the function "add()". The code below should print the sum as an output, in our example it should provide the following output:</p> <p>60</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 print(add(40,20)) 2 def add(n1, n2): 3 return n1 + n2</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code! Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Change the order and move the print statement to the bottom of the code:</p> <pre>def add(n1, n2): return n1 + n2 print(add(40,20))</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Function is called before the function is defined.

F5C2

Task	<p>The code below should return the following output:</p> <p>Name: Emma Salary: 55000 Name: Ben Salary: 46000</p> <p>Given code:</p> <pre>1 def show_employee(name): 2 print("Name:", name, "Salary:", salary) 3 4 show_employee("Emma", 55000) 5 show_employee("Ben")</pre> <p>At the moment, the code is faulty and does not provide the requested output! Identify the error(s) and fix the code. Don't change the last two lines! Rewrite the code in the free text field.</p>
Correct answer	<p>Add the second parameter for the function and set it to the default value 46000 (line 1):</p> <pre>def show_employee(name, salary=46000):</pre>
Expected Error(s)	No understanding of default parameters.

F1C3

Task	Write a program to create a function that accepts two variables and calculates addition and subtraction. Additionally, it must return both addition and subtraction in a single return call.
Correct answer	For example: <pre>def calculation(a, b): return addition = a + b return subtraction = a - b res = calculation(40, 10) print(res)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple.

F2C3

Task	Write a program to create a function that accepts three numbers and finds the largest number along the three numbers. Your code should return the output "Largest number:" plus the actual number.
Correct answer	For example: <pre>def maximum(a, b, c): if (a >= b) and (a >= c): largest = a elif (b >= a) and (b >= c): largest = b else: largest = c return largest res = maximum(2, 4, 7) print("Largest Number: ", res)</pre>
Expected Error(s)	Multiple.